

THE DEVELOPMENT OF PHYSICAL CULTURE AND SPORTS

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Abstract. Forming a healthy lifestyle in our society is of high importance for creating conditions for the population, especially the young generation, as well as regularly engaging them in physical education and mass sports, strengthening the confidence of young people in their will, strength and capabilities through sports competitions, developing feelings of bravery and patriotism, devotion to the country and systematic organization of selection of talented athletes from among young people. Based on this, the main purpose of this article is to reveal the principles of physical culture and sports development in our country.

Keywords: sport, physical education, principles, sportsmen, healthy lifestyle, Republic of Uzbekistan

After gaining state independence in Uzbekistan, great attention was paid to physical education and sports along with culture, education, and science. The constant increase of funds allocated from the state budget is also an indicator of the great attention paid to the field of physical education and sports in the country, which is considered one of the important directions of the state policy. In fact, one of the main reasons for the successful participation of our country's athletes in prestigious international competitions is the regular support of this industry by the state.

In 1992, at the 9th session of the Higher senate of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the adoption of the Law "On Physical Education and Sports", amendments and additions were made to it, and the approval of the new version in 2015 served to further develop the sports sector [2].

Due to the independence, the concept of spiritual purification, restoration of national values, education of a generation was developed, and the idea of national independence, which ensures the development of the Motherland, was formed. New aspects of the Uzbek mentality and national character have been formed. This directly served as a moral basis for radical reforms in the political, economic, social, legal, and educational spheres.

In recent years, consistent measures have been taken to popularize physical education and sports in the republic, to promote a healthy lifestyle among the population, to create the necessary conditions for the physical rehabilitation of persons with limited capabilities, and to ensure the country's appropriate participation in international sports arenas.

At the same time, implementation of specific programs that help to strengthen the health of the population in the field of physical education and sports, wide involvement of young people in sports and selection of talented athletes from among them, skilled athletes who provide high results in sports is a need to form national teams and create additional conditions for trainers.

Therefore, the decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "on measures to further improve and popularize physical education and sports" was adopted [1].

In accordance with this decree, the representatives of our country achieve high results in the Olympic Games, world championships, Asian Games and championships, and international competitions, the prestige and sports potential of Uzbekistan in the world are increasing, and magnificent sports facilities of world standards are built in the territories of our republic. It is especially noteworthy that the three-stage "Sprouts of Hope", "Barkamol Avlod" and Universiade sports games are becoming popular among pupils and students [5, 23].

At the same time, in all regions of our country, it is important to promote the importance of mass sports in human and family life, that it is the basis of physical and mental health, to protect young people entering life with high hopes from harmful habits, to teach them their abilities and talents. There are important and urgent tasks to create the necessary conditions for their realization, to select talented athletes from among them, and to improve the targeted training system.

The main directions of the state policy on the development of physical education and sports are as follows: [3, 47-48]

- state support for the development of physical education and sports;
- ensuring everyone's right to freely engage in physical education and sports;
- harmonization of state and public management in the field of physical education and sports;
- determination of state guarantees of citizens' rights in the field of physical education and sports;
- do not allow discrimination and violence in the field of physical education and sports;
- ensuring the safety of life and health of persons engaged in physical education and sports, as well as participants and spectators of physical education and sports events;
- to support the development of all types and components of sports; - to support the development of physical education and sports among disabled people and other persons with limited physical capabilities, as well as population groups in need of high level of social protection;
- creating conditions for the development and popularization of national sports and folk games;
- ensuring continuity and duration of physical education of citizens;
- implementation of international cooperation.

Also, the following were adopted as the main directions for the development of physical education and sports in the Republic of Uzbekistan: [4, 78-79].

- Improving the system of organization and management of physical education and sports;
- Development of physical education and health promotion, public sports activities and national types of sports;
- Scientific-methodological and medical provision of physical education and sports;
- Development of opportunities of physical education and sports system;
- Promoting physical education and sports;
- Improving the system of providing funds in the field of physical education and sports, developing the non-state sector.

As a result of practical work aimed at the development of physical education and sports in the years of independence:

physical education and health promotion, mass sports and national sports were developed;
the system of providing funds for the field of physical education and sports was improved, the non-state sector was developed;
the material and technical base of physical education and sports was strengthened;
according to the national education program, training and retraining of personnel in the field of physical education and sports was launched.

At the same time, representatives of the population from all social strata are attracted to sports through competitions that cover the population in a mass way. Every year "Kamalot Cup" among youth, workers and employees, culture, law enforcement, defense personnel, sports competitions "Alpomish" for national games, military sports competitions "Shunqorlar" for young people, women's "To'maris" " sports festival, "Courage-will-victory" sports competitions for disabled people, non-stop sports competitions of pupils and students are held regularly.

Based on the decrees of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the decisions of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan, new methods of financial assistance are being used in the lower communities, materially and technically low-income farms in our country. In this, the ways of joint sponsorship of large communities in industry, trade, commerce, construction and many other fields are used. The reason for this is that sponsoring organizations and legal entities will have some benefits in paying taxes on the received income. These aspects are used in sports clubs, national teams, coaches, scientific organizations, medical services and other fields. It is known that there are many charity fund associations operating in our country. Among them, activities such as physical education and sports activities, especially public sports events organized in neighborhoods, financial support of national teams, are included in such activities as "Navroz", "Mahalla", "For a healthy generation", "Ekosan", "Kamalot". and other fund associations are constantly helping.

Conclusion. Based on the information provided above for the development of physical education and sports in our country, it can be concluded that a number of decrees and decisions have been adopted for the development of sports and physical education in the country. Also, a number of principles were defined for the development of physical education and sports, in particular, development of physical education and health, mass sports and national types of sports; Scientific-methodological and medical provision of physical education and sports; Development of possibilities of physical education and sports system; Promotion of physical education and sports; Improving the system of providing funds in the field of physical education and sports, developing the non-state sector. In general, the development of physical education and sports is important in raising a healthy generation.

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